

SMALL SCHOOL STUDENT IN THEIR YOUTH MNEMONIC SKILLS MODERN STUDIES BASED ON IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract. The article talks about impression, imagination, information, perception, R. Burton, consciousness, communication, attention, memorization, etc.

Key words and concepts: Impression, imagination, information, development laws of memory, entering into associative communication, getting a visual impression.

Our country's president Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "Our country and society must do all they can to make our youth independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale and become happy. and we will mobilize our capabilities." Currently, high-level reforms in the field of education are being implemented in our country. In particular, special attention was paid to the field of education, especially to school education, in the video telecast held by the head of our country day and night. Third renaissance period school from the threshold starts saying , emphasizing it's also in vain not Education in giving , it students acceptance to do and their own free thoughts statement to do for of communication importance is incomparable . Especially small school age students to the first stage of school when it comes 237 dialogues in them skill complete not formed will be In the process sociability in raising of memory place big important have the fact that it's not a secret to us .

Modern psychological in the literature subjective laws account received without memory development one how much laws defined :

Remember your stay need has been things about deep , clear , bright impression get need Impression imagination to do with directly depends that it was because of , fantasy and imaginary thinking to develop as well them to manage possibility giving each how also memorizing styles for useful to be can

In man especially strong impression leaving relatively simple life events immediately strong and long time remember stay possible and they are with the first and the only one met from the time starting from a lot years after they in his mind sure and sure manifestation to be can

Man dozen times more complicated and not so much interesting didn't happen events from the head to forgive can , but they in memory long time preserved won't stay

To the event attention with attention directed without , his main thoughts from memory sure and right in order again recovery for him repeatedly from the head forgiveness enough

Information perception in reaching enough of attention lack of his repeated the number increase with cover possible not

A person especially interesting thing never how without difficulty remember remains . This pattern is especially common in adulthood at the age of manifestation will be

Unique , strange , extraordinary impressions familiar , often occurring to impressions than better remember remains .

Under study to the material attention focus , selectivity with together to a person attention to summarize possibility will give and therefore for memory only potential useful information perception reach for setup .

Material better remembering to stay for him as usual from bed before short time inside repetition recommendation will be done . Such without , remembering left thing in memory better stored because that day during usually of each other on top of it coming out and that's it with remembering to stay interrupt giving another impressions with does not interfere and our attention distracts .

We emotional in terms of neutral events about not but in our memory bright , emotional trace left situations about more we think Positive emotions , rule as , to remember help gives negative feelings while to this hindrance does

If memorization during man raised or depressed in the mood if , then remembering to stay on time to him suitable coming emotional the situation artificial respectively recovery memory improves .

First of all , obviously visual impression get need It is stronger . However , it is complicated impressions , that is possibility until more sensations using received impressions necessary the material on the right more better absorb enable gives An example for , Lincoln want to remember has been thing sound out read , that's it perception is both visual and audible .

Caution . If a person the eye suddenly , for example , it is one how many times seen , one how many there is past gone , but pay attention attraction did not of the thing color , shape and again how features presence about to the question answer assuming that it gives if we do , then has been man this object a lot times to what he saw despite , given to the question barely answer give takes

Information to memory input order to him attention to give is a movement .

From this besides , modern psychological in the literature Remember development laws his objective laws account received without highlighted :

Dale Carnegie to repeat of memory second is called the law and the following example brings : " Thousands Muslim students The Qur'an from memory they know , i.e new covenant with one different in length book and they are to this basically repetition through they achieve If we him often to repeat , mind within each how thing remember we will ." Information quantity how much a lot if so , remember to stay for more repetition need will be Volumetric material in parts divided if it is , it's easier remembering remains .

Memorized the material consecutively repetition , known time between such repetitions from distribution according to him memorize for fertile not For example , "One thousand and one " Yesterday " . translator R. Burton own mother

language as twenty seven in the language spoke ; however, he never when one of time in itself ten five per minute more language didn't learn or exercise He admitted that he didn't do it because from this after mind own novelty loses .

new repetition before studied things better remembering to stay help gives

Memorizing to the material of attention increase with him memorize for necessary has been repetitions the number reduce can

Memorize At the beginning of and At the end of from the middle according to relatively a lot repetition it is good

Repetitions day during distribution , material from memory learned to the situation than the time two equal to more saves .

The truth remembering to stay methods one him another fact with is to bind . " In the mind appear to be everyone thing ," says Professor William James [19], - to him the introduction need and from included after , it is already there is has been things with depends will be ... that information takes and they are in the middle closer information installs and they are in the middle closer relationships if installed , they good to memory have will be

For the associative connection of impressions and their subsequent repetition, it is especially important that they are scattered or form a logically connected whole.

The more diverse associations the material evokes during the first acquaintance with it, and the more time is devoted to the mental development of these associations, the better the material itself will be remembered. To relate one fact to another. As you know, you need to think about a new fact from all points of view, and also ask yourself the following questions: "What does it look like?", "What does it look like?", "Why is this?", " How did this happen?", "When will this happen?" and so on.

Any new impression received by a person does not remain special in his memory. Remembering in one form, it can change a little over time, enter into an

associative relationship with other impressions, influence them and, in turn, change under their influence.

Memory efficiency sometimes decreases with noise, i.e. mixing one information with another, one memory scheme with another. Interference often occurs when the same memories are associated with different events in memory, and their presentation in consciousness leads to recall of competing events.

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